

Healing the Ummah:

Restoring the Unity of Faith and Action in Islam

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Reflect on the time when Prophet Muhammad ﷺ was sent as a Messenger. The world was lost in the darkness of ignorance. There were empires like the Roman and Persian empires, but no true justice was being upheld. People lived in aggression, and enmity was rampant; even the blood relations were at odds. Human nature was so degraded that people preyed upon each other. The West was called the “Wild Wild West”, and the Europeans living in caves were described by historians as the “Cavemen”. Then, Allah subhanahu wa ta'ala (SWT) brought love into the hearts of the believers. As He says in Surah Ale-Imran, “He brought your hearts together,—by His grace— you became brothers. And you were on the edge of a pit of the Fire, and He saved you from it” (3:103). Prophet Muhammad ﷺ was sent as a mercy to humanity, guiding them from ignorance into the light of wisdom, and uniting them through the bonds of Islam. By His mercy, people's hearts were brought together, making them brothers in faith. This unity, which saved people from the fire of enmity, was brought about by the message of Islam. The Arabic word ‘Islam’ means ‘submission to the will of Allah’. It is derived from the phrase سَلَامٌ, meaning ‘peace’. Today, Islam is the second-largest religion. One-fourth of the world’s population, i.e., 24.1%, is Muslim (approx. 1.9 billion), and 57 countries on the map of the globe are called Muslim countries.

Allah SWT in the holy Qur'ān assured the believers that the disbelievers would not be able to overpower them, “They will not harm you except for some annoyance. And if they fight you, they will turn their backs and will not be aided” (3:110). Abdullah bin Khabbab bin Al-Aratt narrated from his father, who was present at the Battle of Badr with the Messenger of Allah ﷺ, observed the Prophet ﷺ praying throughout the night until Fajr. Khabbab remarked on the unique nature of the prayer, to which the Prophet ﷺ explained that it was a prayer of hope and fear. In it, he asked Allah SWT for three things:

1. To prevent the destruction of the Ummah as had befallen previous nations — and this was granted.
2. To protect the Ummah from being overwhelmed by enemies from outside — and this was granted.
3. To prevent division within the Ummah into warring factions — and this was not granted. (Jami` at-Tirmidhi (2175))

Despite Allah SWT’s assurance, when we look at the current condition of the Muslim Ummah, we witness widespread oppression and persecution, with Muslims' fundamental human and religious rights being violated, not just by non-Muslim forces, but also by their own Muslim governments. Unlike in the past, when the focus was on shared religious values, common goals, and collective welfare, many -

contemporary Muslim nations now seem to be more concerned with their own territorial, geographical, and racial interests. This shift has led to a fragmentation of the Ummah, where nations prioritize their own political, economic, and national agendas over the broader unity of the Muslim world. As a result, the bonds that once held the Ummah together — based on a common faith, shared struggles, and mutual cooperation — have weakened. This has created divisions that are difficult to bridge, with countries often competing with or even opposing one another instead of working together for the collective good. The question arises: Why is the Ummah today fractured and enduring suffering from both external and internal enemies? This article aims to identify the root cause of the problem and propose solutions to restore unity within the Muslim ummah.

Allah SWT mentioned in the holy Qur'an about two groups: the believers (mu'minin) and the disbelievers (kuffar), each with their alliances—Hizbullah (the Party of Allah) or Hizbul Shaitan (the Party of Satan). The characteristics of believers who are the party of Allah SWT are described in the holy Qur'an as: "You will not find a people who believe in Allah and the Last Day having affection for those who oppose Allah and His Messenger, even if they were their fathers or their sons or their brothers or their kindred" (58:22). While the characteristics of the party of Satan is mentioned as follows: "Satan has overcome them and made them forget the remembrance of Allah (58:19). Yet there is another group of people described by Allah SWT in the holy Qur'an as hypocrites or false believers (munafiqun), "They have taken their oaths as a cover, so they averted [people] from the way of Allah. Indeed, it was evil that they were doing. That is because they believed, and then they disbelieved; so their hearts were sealed over, and they do not understand" (63:1-2).

Allah SWT says in the holy Qur'an, "You are the best nation produced for mankind. You enjoin what is right and forbid what is wrong and believe in Allah" (3:110). Allah (SWT) further guides Muslims regarding the basis for cooperation and unity among the Ummah: "And cooperate in righteousness and piety, but do not cooperate in sin and aggression" (5:2). Allah SWT also warned the believers against forming bonds beyond mere business dealings with those who are not of their faith. He says: "O you who have believed, do not take as intimate allies those outside your ranks, for they will not hesitate to bring you harm. They desire your downfall. Hatred has already manifested from their mouths, and what their hearts conceal is even worse. We have made the signs clear to you, if you would only understand" (3:118).

There are numerous discussion forums, conferences, and dialogues regularly held on the topic of unity and cooperation within the Muslim Ummah. These events often emphasize the importance of solidarity, mutual support, and collective progress among Muslims. However, despite all these efforts, little tangible progress has been made toward actually restoring unity within the Ummah. So, what is the cause of this disunity? Allama Muhammad Iqbal, the 'Poet of the East,' pointed to the cause of the illness of the Ummah in his beautiful poetry by saying:

د نے کہہ بھی دیا 'لا الہ' تو کیا حاصل
دل و نگاہ مسلمان نہیں تو کچھ بھی نہیں

If wit incites a man to say "No God but He"
it brings no gain:

It has no worth at all, Unless affirmed by
heart and brain.

اے شیخ! بہت اچھی مکتب کی فضا، لیکن
بنتی ہے بیابان میں فاروقی و سلمانی

O Shaykh! The atmosphere in the school is
so pleasant,

But only in deserts are people like Faruq
and Salman born.

Allah (SWT) provided the answer to this question in the holy Qur'ān, in Surah Ale-Imran, where He says: “And hold firmly to the rope of Allah all together, and do not become divided” (3:103). In this verse, holding tightly to Allah’s rope is presented as the foundation of unity for the Ummah. What is meant by the “rope of Allah”? It refers to having faith in Allah and His Messenger, obeying their commands and sincerely practising Islamic teaching. This requires the believers to take full responsibility for learning and implementing the teachings of Islam in every aspect of their lives. The “rope of Allah” is what once stopped us from fighting each other, taking each other’s rights, and it made us a people who forgave one another, spent in the way of Allah, and sacrificed for the greater good. However, today, disbelievers are united in their opposition against the believers. If the Ummah is divided, it is crucial to reflect on whether Muslims have abandoned the “rope of Allah”—the very force that once united and protected them from their enemies. Additionally,

Reported by Abu Hurairah (may Allah be pleased with him), the Prophet ﷺ said: “There is no disease that Allah has created, except that He also has created its treatment.”
 مَا أَنْزَلَ اللَّهُ دَاءً إِلَّا أَنْزَلَ لَهُ شِفَاءً (Sahih al-Bukhari 5678).

So, what is the remedy to curb disunity among the Muslim Ummah and how to cure it? In my opinion, the problem today is that most educational systems around the world focus on transferring information—facts and news—without transforming the heart. Knowledge, however, is more than just information. It is a tool that brings change, reshaping the heart and character, and guiding people to live according to the true spirit of Islam. The Prophet ﷺ did not merely teach and transmit words to influence the minds of people; he transformed their hearts and character, guiding his followers to act upon the teachings

of Islam in its true spirit. The knowledge imparted by the Prophet ﷺ is not just informational; it is transformative. It changes beliefs and actions, guiding individuals to a higher moral and spiritual state.

Once Prophet Ibrahim, may Allah be pleased with him, prayed to his Lord: “Our Lord, and send among them a messenger from themselves who will recite to them Your verses and teach them the Book and wisdom and purify them. Indeed, You are the Exalted in Might, the Wise” (2:129). Allah SWT fulfilled His promise by sending the seal of the prophethood, Prophet Muhammad ﷺ, as a mercy to all mankind until the day of judgement. He mentions in the holy Qur'ān: “It is He who has sent among the unlettered a Messenger from themselves reciting to them His verses and purifying them and teaching them the Book and wisdom - although they were before in clear error” (62:2). From these verses we can see that the Prophet Muhammad was sent to fulfil four responsibilities, these are: to recite to them (the people) the verses of the holy Qur'ān, to purify their soul, to teach them the book and to teach them the wisdom.

The knowledge brought by Prophet Muhammad ﷺ is rooted in both sharī'ah and ṭarīqah. Sharī'ah is the law, the scholarship, and the knowledge brought by the messenger about 'ibādah and mu'āmalāt. Whereas ṭarīqah is the sincere practice and implementation of those teachings ordered in

sharī'ah. There are four renowned madh'hab or schools of thought within Islamic jurisprudence, pertaining to the outer dimension of human conduct. The major Sunni madhāhib are Mālikī, Ḥanafī, Shāfi'ī, and Ḥanbalī. On the other hand, to transform the inner dimension of human conduct and to purify their soul, Islam's mystical-ascetic dimension, known as Taṣawwuf or Sufism, deals with the purification of the inner self by focusing on the spiritual aspect, which is represented by schools or orders known as Salasil-e- Taṣawwuf/Ṭarīqah. The four renowned Salasil taṣawwuf are: al-Ṭarīqa al-Qādiriyya, al-Ṭarīqa al-Suhrawardī, al-Ṭarīqa al-Naqshbandī, and al-Ṭarīqa al-Chishtī.

Before the Muslim lands were colonized, the madāris (Islamic schools) taught the core subjects of Islam, such as the Qur'ān, 'ilm al-tafsīr (knowledge of interpretation), 'ilm al-hadith (knowledge of prophetic traditions), fiqh (jurisprudence), sarf (morphology), and nahu (grammar) along with the physical sciences. Meanwhile, the khānaqāh (Sufi centers) played a crucial role in tazkiyah—the purification of hearts and intentions—preparing students to enter the practical world with a sound moral and spiritual foundation. Although there may be some minor differences in the furū' (secondary) aspects of Islamic teachings, all believers are united in the uṣūl (fundamental) principles of Islam.

Muslims can find common ground despite minor differences between madh'hab if they follow the original approach of the imams, who sought to promote unity within the ummah. These differences, being of a secondary nature, should not become a cause for disunity among Muslims. The Imams of each madh'hab themselves advised their followers to adhere primarily to the Qur'ān and Sunnah as the ultimate sources of guidance in their fiqh rulings. These imams did not encourage divisions but instead urged their students to prioritize the Qur'ān (the “rope of

Allah”) and the Sunnah above all personal opinions. By doing so, the Ummah can overcome the divisions and animosities that have arisen between the various madh'hab. Allah SWT also reminds Muslims about their state of affairs, He says: And how could you disbelieve while to you are being recited the verses of Allah and among you is His Messenger? And whoever holds firmly to Allah has [indeed] been guided to a straight path” (3:101).

For the Muslim Ummah to achieve true unity today, it is essential to align 'īmān (faith), 'aqīdah (beliefs), and 'amal (actions)—that is, to hold firmly to the “rope of Allah” by adhering to the principles of Islam as taught by Prophet Muhammad (PBUH). This can be realized by transforming our educational system to nurture both the outer and inner dimensions of human conduct. True success, both in this world and the Hereafter, lies in following Allah's guidance in every aspect of life, which is best achieved by following the Sunnah (practices of Prophet Muhammad) of Prophet Muhammad ﷺ. Allah (SWT) says in the Qur'ān: “Say, [O Muhammad], If you love Allah, then follow me, and Allah will love you and forgive you your sins. And Allah is Forgiving and Merciful” (3:31). May Allah SWT grant us the strength to hold tightly to His “rope,” for there is no refuge for a believer outside the protection of Islam.